

Declarations and Statements for supplementary material for the
following preprint: The relationship between player tracking data
and individual risk factors in online sports bettors: an explorative
study

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Declarations and Statements

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Disclosure statement

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Data availability statement

The datasets presented in this article are not readily available because we received sensitive information like player tracking data. The raw data might be attributed to individuals by the provider, which is why we have to apply further anonymization processes like aggregation before making the data available. This is why we will only be able to make the data available after we have finished the data collection / procession and applied further anonymization procedures to comply with data protection rights and ensure the participants’ anonymity. This will supposedly take place in autumn 2024. Once this is completed, we will make the anonymized data available. Data remaining sensitive will then be available upon reasonable request, i.e. for further research within the used open repository (controlled access) or only in aggregated form.

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